

Implementing Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) in Teaching English to Non-Linguistic Specialities Students

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ABSTRACT

Language, being the main means of communication, is used in all activities of the subject. The task of the teacher is to determine the main educational action and subordinate integrated actions, to model the conditions under which the latter can become the assimilation of the former. The CLIL program sets itself two global goals, namely: a sufficient level of study of a school subject through a foreign language, as well as a deep study of a foreign language through the subjects taught. Thanks to this approach, teaching students in their native and target languages is one continuous process. Foreign language lessons provide the teacher with great opportunities for the implementation of interdisciplinary connections. The article deals with the issues based on implementing content and language integrated learning (CLIL) in teaching English to the students of non-linguistic universities.

Keywords: educational action, approach, content and language integrated learning, non-linguistic universities.

INTRODUCTION

An integrated approach to teaching a foreign language is a condition for the formation and development of a versatile personality. We understand the term "integration" as the concept of a state of connectedness of separate differentiated parts into a single whole, as well as the pedagogical process itself leading to this state. The explanatory dictionary of foreign words gives the following definition: integration is the unification of parts, elements, this is the side of the development process associated with unification into a single whole. The idea of integration in education originates in the works of the great didactic Ya.A. Comenius, who stated: "Everything that is connected with each other must be constantly connected

and distributed proportionally between the mind, memory and language. Thus, everything that is taught to a person should not be scattered and partial, but one and whole. Integration is becoming one of the most important and promising methodological directions in the formation of a new education.

DISCUSSIONS

Integration in learning is the subordination of the single goal of educating and teaching the same type of parts and elements of content, methods and forms within the educational system at a certain level of education.

In the scientific and pedagogical literature, integrated courses are considered as a didactic tool for the controlled integration of knowledge acquired by students in the process of forming interdisciplinary skills.

The correct introductions of integrated courses, their skillful use are important for developing the flexibility of the mind of students and activating the learning process, and in this case, for strengthening the practical orientation of teaching a foreign language. At the same time, it is important to achieve the optimal combination of goals in an integrated language learning course. Interdisciplinary connections are becoming very relevant at the present stage of development of school and vocational education, the improvement of which goes along the path of knowledge integration, which does not at all mean the elimination of systematic courses of individual subjects. They only contribute to strengthening the practical orientation of the subject "foreign language".

The problem occupies an important place in pedagogy, psychology and methods of teaching not only a foreign language, but also other theoretical and practical disciplines. Its relevance remains due to its versatility, as well as the complexity of implementation.

This study reflects and describes the state of integrated learning today. When developing this study, the method of analyzing psychological and pedagogical literature on the topic and the method of content analysis were used.

Profound changes in social, political, economic life have a great influence on the development of the education system. The education system is faced with the task of preparing schoolchildren for cultural, professional and personal communication with representatives of countries with different social traditions, social structure and linguistic culture. This task should be solved from childhood, starting from kindergarten, etc. In educational policy, this reorientation has led to the creation of integrated courses of study. Integration is one of the conditions for learning, which ensures the proper assimilation of a foreign language and the course that is used in direct connection with the language. Integrated teaching of a foreign language is due to a variety of pedagogical, psychological and methodological factors.

The problem of the formation of integrated courses also affects the issue of educational and methodological support. There is a need to create special teaching aids, the task of which is to provide students with complete knowledge of one or another integrated foreign language course.

In the process of conducting such classes, it is important to diversify the content and form of the activities of students, which include consolidated knowledge and which will ensure the assimilation of methods for the specific use of knowledge. A variety of games can diversify such activities, because. in the process of games, the development of the psyche takes place, the content is assimilated, a system of significant skills and abilities is formed (1.48). In addition to increasing the effectiveness of learning, games contribute to the manifestation of a distinct practical orientation of a foreign language.

Speaking about the problem of the formation of integrated learning, the following should be taken into account: in order to prepare a lesson or a course, it is necessary to focus on three aspects - subject-content, language and communicative (9.73). Failure to meet one of them makes integrated learning impossible.

Content and language integrated learning is determined by the necessary level of informativeness. It is necessary to select in advance the amount of factual knowledge on the topic that is needed for the unprepared speech of the trainees on the main issues of the topic.

Unlike traditional programs, integrated language programs form polysystemic knowledge about the language. In such programs, mastering monosystemic knowledge of a foreign language is not a goal, but a means in understanding the relationships and external interactions with other monosystems.

As you know, the program traditionally fixes the goals, the content of training, the sequence of mastering and the requirements for the level of proficiency in speech skills. In accordance with the goal-setting function, the program of an integrated course for studying a foreign language should, first of all, reveal the goals that are determined by the modern order of society. In terms of in-depth study of the integrated course, the study of a foreign language involves:

1) increase the motivation to learn a foreign language by saturating the course with interesting information and involving students in practical matters using a foreign language;

2) to make foreign language knowledge, skills and abilities practically more targeted, focused on specific areas of application;

3) to ensure the strength of this knowledge, skills and abilities based on an increase in the volume of speech practice, both in terms of reception (reading, listening) and production (speaking, writing);

To create a holistic view of the real world in the student. The result of such integration is that the child receives the knowledge about the world that reflects the connectivity of individual parts of the world as a system.

The goals determine its content, which, in order to better manage the educational process, can be correlated in the program with the communicative tasks to be solved, new language material, expected speech products and the final planned learning outcome. Integration is finding a common platform for convergence of subject knowledge at the junction of existing traditional subject knowledge, children receive more and more new ideas about the world, systematically replenishing and expanding them (moving in knowledge in a spiral.

Integrated learning can take place at various levels. They are distinguished by three levels of integration in the lesson

At the first level, the main source of integration is direct intersubject communications. The allocation of this level in a comprehensive program of integrated teaching of a foreign language is associated with the tasks of coordinating the teaching of the relevant material. It is especially important to designate the proposed material in a single program to ensure a coordinated choice of vocabulary and topics for foreign language classes.

The second level involves the implementation of the integration of basic education (the so-called "basic element") and additional classes in subjects ("school element"). In addition to expanding the material, the second level also implies a higher quality of interdisciplinary connections, episodic inclusion of material from other subjects. Direct didactic synthesis is possible - conducting joint

thematic classes on the basis of new material in two or more disciplines in a foreign language. It is the access to the second level that can make it possible to logically and effectively solve the tasks of strengthening the sociocultural orientation of foreign language education in general, expanding background knowledge of a foreign language, modernizing the lexical base and strengthening the motivational aspect of teaching foreign languages.

The allocation of the third level is associated with a certain thematic limitation of subject courses. The very logic of building current programs of the studied disciplines clearly outlines not only the problems of the foreign language taught within their framework, but also possible directions for deepening its study. Thus, the third level assumes the highest level of integrated learning, associated with the transition from coordination to a deep synthesis of knowledge in a foreign language in connection with the course being taught, from the construction of interdisciplinary didactic systems to the formation of a new educational discipline of an integrated nature. The subject of analysis are multifaceted objects, information about the essence of which is contained in various disciplines, the independence of each subject with its own goals, objectives, program is preserved.

Basics of the CLIL teaching methodology:

- Knowledge of the language becomes a means of mastering the program of the subject being studied.
- Classes are held in an exciting way: students do not just go through the standard program, but conduct various experiments, make discoveries and make scientific experiments.
- The language in which all classes are conducted is integrated into the general education curriculum.

- The structure and content of the lessons increase students' motivation to learn to speak the language and use it so that they can discuss various interesting topics with their classmates.
- Classes are aimed at complete immersion in the language environment.
- A necessary skill that all students must master is fluent reading of texts in English.

To solve the tasks set, the following theoretical methods were used: analysis of the literature on the application of the CLIL approach in teaching a foreign language to students, the use of digital tools in this process, which makes it possible to determine the features of integrated subject-language learning in a distance environment; analysis of programs and teaching aids in English and profile disciplines studied by students of the specialty "Design of technological machines and complexes", which contributes to the definition of content for organizing training based on CLIL; designing sections of the course "Foreign language in professional activity" based on the given characteristics in order to develop a new content of training. The following empirical methods were also used: a methodological experiment aimed at testing the designed model in the process of teaching students of non-linguistic faculties.

The theoretical basis of the study was scientific works that reveal the principles of organizing integrative subject-language education (A. A. Sirotova [16], K. S. Grigoryeva, L. L. Salekhova [4]) and studies that represent the basics of introducing CLIL into teaching a foreign language. language in a non-linguistic university (E. V., Kartsevoi, A. A. Flaksman [8], O. A. Chekun [18]), which made it possible to establish a strategy for selecting special material and the form of its presentation, aimed at developing a set of students' skills; scientific and methodological works that describe the conditions for introducing CLIL into

teaching (N. V. Popova et al. [4], O. V. Kuznetsova [1]), and works that determine how to use digital technologies to optimize the teaching of a foreign language to students (N V. Malinina [1], T. M. Guloy, S. A. Romanova [5]), which contributed to the identification of the necessary foundations for creating a digital educational environment for teaching the discipline "Foreign language in professional activity" for future engineers.

The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that the model presented in the article for introducing the foundations of CLIL into teaching future engineers English in a digital educational environment and the methods for its implementation, disclosed in the course of describing the methodological experiment, can be used by teachers of the discipline "Foreign Language in Professional Activities" in non-linguistic faculties to improve the quality of student learning.

The key orientation for teaching English to students of non-linguistic university today is teaching a language for special purposes (ESP - English for Specific Purposes), which involves the connection of language material with professionally oriented content. Defining the differences between ESP and CLIL, W. Yang (W. Yang) says that university students want to receive subject knowledge in the course of learning a foreign language, which brings ESP closer to CLIL. If in the ESP approach the emphasis is on providing the student with a sufficient level of language skills to master the subject content, then CLIL assumes a focus on the language material and subject [2]. The essence of the CLIL method is in the possibility of forming a student's foreign language communicative competence in the same context in which the formation and development of knowledge and skills take place [3]. The basic principle of the CLIL approach is "4C", including content (selection of professionally directed material), culture

(immersion in a different cultural environment), cognition (development of a complex of students' mental skills), communication (development of foreign language communication skills of students) [2]. D. Coyle, presenting the "4C" principle, notes that the content, cultural and cognitive components are realized through communication [2]. That is, CLIL should be considered as an environment for creating subject-oriented communication based on acquired knowledge, developing thinking skills and recognizing cultural aspects.

The analysis of works devoted to the study of CLIL in teaching a foreign language to students of a non-linguistic university allows us to identify the following features of using this approach:

- the main linguodidactic unit is an authentic text, which serves as a starting point for further discussion and presentation of linguistic material [1];
- the priority format of learning within CLIL is work in pairs, groups (cooperative learning) [4];
- Emphasis is placed on the development of communication skills: fluent speech, during which mistakes are perceived as a natural part of learning [7].

Along with the advantages, researchers [5] indicate the problems of introducing this approach into the real educational practice of a non-linguistic university. These include an insufficient level of foreign language proficiency among students of non-linguistic university to implement the principles of CLIL; the complexity of the interaction of foreign language teachers with teachers of special disciplines, the unpreparedness of teachers for the integration of knowledge; insufficient number of hours in the discipline "Foreign language" in non-linguistic university. Despite the identified problems, the use of CLIL is a priority in the organization of education, which allows students to be motivated and achieve high results.

It is worth noting that there are different models of CLIL implementation: “soft”, soft CLIL (integration of professionally oriented topics into a foreign language course) and “hard”, hard CLIL (teaching topics of professional discipline in a foreign language) [18]. The most acceptable option for teaching a multi-level group of students of non-linguistic university in the distance learning format is a "soft" model (soft CLIL). Determining the possibilities of its successful implementation in the teaching of "Foreign language in professional activities", we agree with K.S. Grigoryeva that the conditions for the productive functioning of CLIL are the use of authentic texts, the teacher's assistance in minimizing language difficulties, active interaction of students, and the development of higher-order thinking skills [3].

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, the use of the basics of CLIL contributes to the development of foreign language communicative competence of students, as well as increasing their motivation to learn English and the emergence of a whole range of “soft” competencies (the ability to interact effectively in a team, use digital technologies, self-organize their own activities and self-development) that increase the competitiveness of a specialist in the modern world. As a promising direction for further research, we consider the development of integrated classes in English and professional discipline based on the proposed model.

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